

Research article

Analyzing policy mixes for the circular economy transition: The case of recycled plastics in electronics[☆]

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ABSTRACT

This study analyzes how policy mixes influence the transition to a circular plastics economy, focusing on recycling in the electrical and electronic equipment (EEE) sector. Our research contributes to the literature on how policy mixes can accelerate sustainability transitions by proposing an adjusted framework tailored to the circular economy transition. We use qualitative content analysis of 14 EU legislative documents and conduct 20 semi-structured interviews with actors across the plastics and EEE value chain. We find that the current policy mix is not conducive to promoting this transition and highlight three key barriers. First, we find short-term inconsistencies between increasing plastic recycling rates and tightening chemical regulations on hazardous substances. Second, we identify a lack of economic incentives to stimulate demand for recycled content and note the absence of harmonized, mandatory criteria for defining end-of-waste and recycled content. Finally, coordination between product users, producers, and recycling operators shows deficits.

1. Introduction

The world today faces many sustainability challenges, such as climate change and biodiversity loss, which present significant environmental risks and create social and economic problems for humanity (Markard et al., 2012). Addressing these challenges requires sustainability transitions — multi-dimensional processes in which socio-technical systems transform towards sustainable ways of consumption and production (Markard et al., 2012; Turnheim and Geels, 2013). Given the complexity and uncertainty of these transitions, policy intervention is essential to shape their pace and trajectory (Van den Bergh, 2013; Head and Alford, 2015; Kern and Markard, 2016). Policymakers worldwide have responded with measures to promote more sustainable living (International Resource Panel, 2011; European Environmental Agency, 2019). To address multiple goals and market failures, they often combine various instruments and strategies into a *policy mix* (Flanagan et al., 2011; Del Río, 2014; Rogge and Reichardt, 2016). Over the past decade, scholars have extensively studied how *policy mixes* influence the direction and speed of sustainability transitions (Markard et al., 2012) in different contexts, including the renewable energy transition (Reichardt and Rogge, 2016; Koch et al., 2022; Zepa and Hoffmann, 2023) or sustainable water management (Ingold et al., 2016; Pakizer et al., 2020). However, much less is known

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about their design and impact on other sustainability areas, such as the circular economy transition. To address this gap, we apply the policy mix concept to study the policy landscape governing the circular economy transition for plastics in the EU. Our analysis adapts the existing policy mix framework to better capture the characteristics of this transition.

To address the severe threats posed by linear plastics production, use, and end-of-life management (Arp et al., 2021; MacLeod et al., 2021; Cabernard et al., 2022), researchers and practitioners have introduced roadmaps for transitioning to a circular plastics economy (Arp et al., 2021; Bachmann et al., 2023). In an ideal circular plastics economy, environmental footprints are decreased to respect planetary boundaries by (i) reducing plastic demand, (ii) substituting fossil-based plastics with recycled or bio-based alternatives, (iii) minimizing plastic waste through increased recycling or reuse, and (iv) avoiding hazardous substances in plastic formulations (World Economic Forum, 2016; Stegmann et al., 2022; Bachmann et al., 2023; Vidal et al., 2024). This transition requires innovations across the plastics life-cycle, including changes in product design (Fenwick et al., 2023), advances in recycling technologies (Vogt et al., 2021), and new business models and supply chain practices (Haswell et al., 2024). National governments, intergovernmental, and international organizations are increasingly taking active roles in the circular economy for plastics by advancing plans and policy measures to accelerate the transition (see, e.g., Canadian Council of Ministers of the Environment, 2018; Flynn et al., 2019; Yee, 2023; World Bank Group, 2024). For example, the European Union (EU) introduced a European Plastics Strategy in 2018, outlining key policy instruments and legal revisions (European Commission, 2018a).

Arguably, the circular plastics transition presents specific challenges to policy mix design that require a tailored policy landscape analysis. First, policy mixes promoting a circular plastics transition must balance circularity with other objectives (Korhonen et al., 2018; Blum et al., 2020; Velenturf and Purnell, 2021; Yang et al., 2023), such as reducing chemical pollution, protecting biodiversity, or ensuring resilient internal markets (European Commission, 2020). Second, the policies governing plastics circularity need to operate at the intersection of different legislative domains, such as waste, product, and chemical legislation, where each may have its distinct reasoning and legacy (European Commission, 2018b; Friege et al., 2019; Johansson and Krook, 2021; Alaranta and Turunen, 2021; de Waal, 2021, 2023). Finally, as the circular economy transition will bring about a reconfiguration of the value chain (Kanda et al., 2021; Reike et al., 2023), policy mixes governing circular plastics must facilitate this restructuring and moderate its consequences.

In this article, we study the policy mix governing plastic circularity for the specific case of the electrical and electronic equipment (EEE) sector in the EU. Electronic products, such as smartphones, washing machines, and refrigerators, consist of 20%–30% plastic components on average (Parajuly et al., 2017; Huisman et al., 2017; Baldé et al., 2024), and their global production is expected to increase substantially in the coming decade (Baldé et al., 2024). We combine an analysis of the policy mix governing plastics in electronics with a specific focus on one circular economy strategy, recycling, since the EU has identified it as one of the critical areas for policy intervention (European Commission, 2020). The diverse composition of materials and polymers in electronics (Babbitt et al., 2020; Bill et al., 2019), the presence of hazardous chemicals (Wagner and Schlummer, 2020; Fjäder et al., 2022), and the lack of reliable data on quantity and composition of e-plastics (Cardamone et al., 2021; Baldé et al., 2024) make plastics recycling particularly challenging in this sector. In 2022 only about 3% of the plastics used in EEE products in Europe are sourced from recycled material (Plastics Europe, 2022). In this study, we pose the research question:

What is the current EU policy mix governing plastics recycling in EEE, and how does it contribute to increasing recycling and the uptake of recycled plastics in electronic products?

This article makes three main theoretical contributions: First, we introduce a new instrument classification category, *life-cycle safety & traceability*, alongside supply-push and demand-pull instruments. This addition more accurately reflects the need for policy mixes in the circular economy for plastics to ensure the safety of materials for human health and the environment at all life-cycle stages. It allows for a more holistic assessment of how safety and traceability instruments across waste, product, and chemical legislation interlink and clarifies that user safety – typically captured under product legislation – is also a function of safety instruments defined in waste and chemical legislation. Second, we build on recent policy mix studies, focusing on policy mix characteristics (see, e.g. Bach and Hansen, 2023) and propose *coordination* at the value chain level as a new characteristic. Coordination is increasingly recognized in different literature streams as critical for managing the complex multi-level and multi-actor settings of transitions (Elzinga et al., 2023). In the circular economy transition, we argue that coordination is essential for capturing how well the policy mix facilitates value chain restructuring. Second, following Mavrot et al. (2019), we add a value chain perspective to the policy mix framework initially developed by Rogge and Reichardt (2016). We argue that this perspective is necessary for assessing policy mixes through *life-cycle thinking*, a vital principle of the circular economy (De Laurentiis et al., 2024). The value chain perspective helps identify where, along the life-cycle, legal drivers and barriers occur, allowing for a more nuanced assessment of policy mixes.

Empirically, we contribute to the literature by providing a descriptive overview of the regulatory and policy landscape for recycling electronics, e-waste, and plastics (see, e.g. Kautto and Lazarevic, 2020; Barouta et al., 2022; Diana et al., 2022; de Waal, 2023). We identify key EU strategy and policy documents governing plastics circularity and present a detailed list of the most relevant policy instruments for recycling in the EEE sector. By combining legal text analysis with semi-structured interviews, we go beyond a descriptive analysis of the policy mix, identifying policy drivers and barriers to plastic recycling. These findings offer crucial insights to policymakers at the early implementation stage of the policy mix.

The rest of the article is structured as follows: In Section 2, we describe the theoretical framework for analyzing policy mixes, including the three characteristics of interest. Sections 3 and 4 describe the research case and methods applied to study the policy mix. Section 5 outlines the results of our policy analysis, while Section 6 provides a discussion of these results and outlines the study's limitations.

2. Theoretical background

This section outlines the policy mix theory used to evaluate the policy landscape for plastics recycling. The first subsection details the key components of the policy mix and discusses the need for a tailored approach to assess policy mixes within the context of circular economy transitions for plastics. The following subsections will provide a more in-depth description of the proposed changes.

2.1. Policy mixes for the circular economy transition

A *policy mix* can be understood as the combination of multiple policy instruments to achieve policy objectives in settings where a single instrument does not suffice to address all goals or market failures (Flanagan et al., 2011; Del Río, 2014; Schmidt and Sewerin, 2019). Rogge and Reichardt (2016) provide a comprehensive framework that synthesizes different ways of conceptualizing and analyzing policy mixes between multiple disciplines. The framework links the policy mix to sustainability transitions and provides an extensive overview of analytical features that can be considered for analyzing and evaluating policy mixes. According to Rogge and Reichardt (2016), policy mixes consist of three main building blocks: elements, characteristics, and processes. The latter refers to the dynamics of policy making along all stages of the policy cycle that eventually determine the set of policy mix elements (Rogge and Reichardt, 2016). Since this study aims to evaluate the functioning of the current policy mix for plastics circularity for the electronics sector, we focus our analysis on policy mix elements and characteristics without considering its evolution over time.

Whereas the policy mix concept has been applied in various sustainability contexts, ranging from renewable energy technologies (Rogge and Schleich, 2018) to pollution control for maritime shipping (Bach and Hansen, 2023), relatively few studies conceptualize or evaluate policy mixes for the circular plastics transition. Those investigating policies for the transition towards a circular economy (for different materials and sectors) have highlighted three key challenges for policymakers when designing successful CE policies. Firstly, a sustainable circular economy transition will require balancing the different objectives of material circularity with environmental, economic, and social objectives, such as reducing pollution from hazardous substances and generating jobs (Blum et al., 2020). Policy mixes, thus, need to be designed for multiple, possibly contradicting, purposes. Secondly, CE policy must operate at the entire life-cycle of products and lie at the intersection between waste, product, and chemical legislation (European Commission, 2018b; Alaranta and Turunen, 2021; Johansson and Krook, 2021). These regulatory domains tend to be separated and follow different principles – i.e., hazard vs risk approaches (Scheer et al., 2014; Johansson and Krook, 2021) – which may create problems when designing policy mixes. Lastly, the circular economy transition of plastics will require the restructuring of the linear value chain and connecting value chain steps that have not been connected before (Kanda et al., 2021; Reike et al., 2023). Effective policy mixes for CE will thus need to facilitate information and feedback loops between all actors of the value chain (Wilts and O'Brien, 2019).

Given these challenges, we argue that the existing policy mix framework may not be sufficient to give a complete assessment of the policy landscape that addresses circular economy transitions for different materials and sectors. We, therefore, propose three main features to be added to the existing framework that ensure a better fit of the concept in the context of the circular economy. These features refer to (1) changes in the classification of policy instruments that are part of the *policy mix elements*, (2) introducing new *policy mix characteristics* to evaluate the performance of the mix, and (3) adding the *value chain perspective* as an additional dimension to policy mix evaluation. Our adjusted framework is illustrated in Fig. 1, and each feature is described in more depth in the following sections.

2.2. Policy mix elements: classification of instruments

The *elements* describe the main content of the policy mix, including instruments and strategies. The latter can be understood as long-term objectives and principal plans often combined with quantitative targets (Schmidt et al., 2012; Rogge and Reichardt, 2016). Policy instruments are the formal means by which policy objectives are achieved (Rogge and Reichardt, 2016; Salamon, 2002). Instruments are contained in policies and have been classified by their type, purpose, and design features (Rogge and Reichardt, 2016; Sterner and Coria, 2013; Jaffe et al., 2002). Recent studies that estimate the effectiveness of policy mixes for the case of the renewable energy transition highlight that policy outcomes are susceptible to the exact configuration of policy mix elements in particular as different instrument purposes can play unique roles in the transition (Schmidt and Sewerin, 2019; Nunez-Jimenez et al., 2022).

In this article, we rely on the classification matrix used in Rogge and Reichardt (2016) and divide instruments by their type and purpose. Following the most common conceptualization in the literature, we distinguish between information, regulation, and economic instruments (Vedung, 1998). We understand economic instruments or *carrots* as fiscal and other economic (dis)incentives that affect the behavior of actors through changes in prices (OECD, 2024). Regulatory instruments, or *sticks*, are binding regulatory provisions commonly tied to compliance rules and sanctions for non-compliance. Information instruments, or *sermons*, are typically non-binding and non-financial instruments such as educative campaigns aimed at consumers (Vedung, 1998; The World Bank, 1998; Sterner and Coria, 2013).¹ When classifying instrument purposes for policy mixes in CE transitions, we distinguish between supply-push and demand-pull instruments in line with Nemet (2009) and Peters et al. (2012).² Supply-push instruments describe all policy

¹ In this paper, several information-type regulatory provisions – such as mandatory product labeling or mandatory information provision to consumers – were classified as regulatory instruments.

² Note that we use the term supply push and technology push interchangeably.

Fig. 1. Illustration of the policy mix framework.

Notes: This figure summarizes the analytical framework used in this study adopted from Rogge and Reichardt (2016). As indicated, this study focuses on two (of three) main building blocks of policy mixes: elements and characteristics.

instruments aimed at increasing the supply of circular materials. In contrast, demand-pull instruments stimulate the demand for recycled, reused, and other circular products and materials. We propose to add the category *life-cycle safety & traceability* as a third category.³ This category encompasses policy instruments designed to ensure materials remain safe for human health and the environment throughout their life-cycle while maintaining traceability. It includes instruments for user safety, particularly producer responsibilities during product use, as well as safety and quality measures in earlier life-cycle stages, such as production & distribution. In a circular economy context, these instruments warrant safety and quality in second-life-cycles, such as during and after material and substance recycling (Ellsworth-Krebs et al., 2022). Life-cycle traceability complements these instruments and enables circular economy implementation by facilitating comprehensive capture, storage, and sharing of safety and quality information across product life-cycles (Rumetshofer and Fischer, 2023; Corallo et al., 2020). In the context of the circular economy transition, the role of life-cycle safety & traceability instruments is, hence, to ensure that safety is not compromised during the circulation of materials and to enhance traceability, thereby indirectly facilitating material circulation. The inclusion of this category thus reflects the challenge faced by circular economy policies in aligning the goals of increasing material circularity with protecting human health and the environment from hazardous substances.

2.3. Policy mix characteristics: Consistency, comprehensiveness, coordination

Policy mix *characteristics* emerge from the interaction of instruments and strategies and serve as critical criteria to evaluate the performance of the policy mix design — in particular at an early stage of its implementation when other performance indicators do not exist (Rogge and Reichardt, 2016; Mavrot et al., 2019). They can be evaluated at the vertical (i.e., across governance levels) and horizontal (i.e., across different policies) level. Recent literature has highlighted that characteristics, such as the perceived credibility, consistency, and comprehensiveness, are positively associated with policy mix performance in different settings (Reichardt and Rogge, 2016; Rogge and Schleich, 2018; Li et al., 2020; Bach and Hansen, 2023; Zepa and Hoffmann, 2023).

We argue for including at least three policy mix characteristics when analyzing policy mixes in CE. The characteristics, consistency, comprehensiveness, and coordination reflect the key CE-specific challenges for policy-making.

Consistency in a policy mix represents a state where different policy elements exist in symmetry and alignment without contradictions (De Baere, 2008; Herlin-Karnell and Konstadinides, 2013). When policy strategies and instruments create trade-offs

³ In this way, our conceptualization follows Taylor (2008) who attested that an improvement of the policy purpose classification is needed as not to leave distinct purposes of policies unexplained.

or incompatibilities, the policy mix becomes inconsistent, leading to increased uncertainty and impeded achievement of overarching policy goals (Del Río, 2014; Rogge and Reichardt, 2016; de Waal, 2021).⁴ In the context of CE, such inconsistencies may occur in particular when balancing between different overarching objectives (Blum et al., 2020; Johansson and Krook, 2021) or between different circularity strategies (Reike et al., 2018).

Comprehensiveness of the mix refers to the level of exhaustiveness and completeness of elements and processes (Atuahene-Gima and Murray, 2004; Miller, 2008; Rogge and Reichardt, 2016). A mix is considered comprehensive if it contains all types (regulatory, economic, information) and all purposes (supply-push, demand-pull, life-cycle safety & traceability) of policy instruments. For example, a mix can be deemed incomprehensive if it does not address all market failures or contains obvious gaps regarding policy instruments or strategies. Comprehensiveness is of particular concern for policy mixes in the circular economy context. Policy analysis has to evaluate whether the mix covers the entire life-cycle of a material or whether any gaps remain between the different legislative domains, such as the waste, product, and chemical legislation (Friege et al., 2019; Alaranta and Turunen, 2021).

We propose to add the new characteristic *coordination* to the policy mix framework. Coordination has been identified as a central feature in multi-level and multi-actor settings such as the circular economy transition. In line with Elzinga et al. (2023), we define coordination as the degree to which the policy mix involves and empowers different actors and introduces well-aligned strategies and instruments along the value chain. For the circular economy transition, examining the coordination of the policy mix is crucial to understanding how well it moderates the value chain reconfiguration processes that make up an integral part of the transition. A coordinated policy mix will contain instruments and strategies that address all relevant value chain actors and creates interfaces between different fragmented parts. Lack of coordination can, for example, arise if the mix fails to provide interfaces between different actors or does not establish relevant information and feedback flows along the value chain (Wilts and O'Brien, 2019). Note that our definition of coordination refers explicitly to the value chain level and not to the vertical coordination of different policy bodies, e.g., EU and member states. In the latter context, coordination is often defined as the process of achieving a policy mix that is coherent between different government levels (Flanagan et al., 2011; Rogge and Reichardt, 2016).

2.4. Value chain level: additional dimension to policy mix evaluation

While the policy mix framework focuses on assessing the design of instruments and strategies, the *actor groups* these measures target are often overlooked. Yet, it is the response of these target actors to policy interventions that ultimately leads to change (Mavrot et al., 2019). In the context of the circular economy transition, *value chain actors* are a particularly central actor group, as policy mixes must moderate and facilitate innovation and restructuring processes across the entire value chain. Following Mavrot et al. (2019), we propose broadening the focus to the *recipient side* of policy mixes and integrating a value chain perspective into policy mix theory.

We define value chain actors as the economic actors that are involved in the various steps that lead to the consumption (i.e., upstream material supply, processing, product design, and distribution) and final disposal of goods after use in the sector of interest (Kaplinsky and Morris, 2000; Sturgeon, 2001). Different policy instruments can target various actors, offering distinct resources and incentives to each (Pierson, 1993; Edmondson et al., 2019). Therefore, we propose classifying policy instruments by their type, purpose, and the specific value chain actor they target. We argue that integrating the value chain level allows for a more nuanced evaluation of policy mixes. As illustrated in Fig. 1, this approach reveals *where* legal drivers and barriers exist *within the value chain*, offering a valuable complement to the analysis of policy mix characteristics. Incorporating the value chain level helps to identify the value chain steps left unaddressed by the policy mix or can point out where gaps, conflicts, and misalignment predominantly occur.

3. Research case

In this study, we apply our adjusted policy mix framework to assess how the policy mix governing circular plastics affects plastics recycling and the use of recycled plastics content in the electrical and electronic equipment (EEE) sector. While electronic products generally consist of a wide range of materials, plastics constitute an average of 20%–30% of their mass (Parajuly et al., 2017; Huisman et al., 2017). In light of the projected rising consumption of EEE products (Baldé et al., 2024), the amount of plastic waste fractions stemming from these products is expected to increase further within the next decade. This presents considerable challenges for the collection and recycling activities to keep pace (Forti et al., 2020) while worsening adverse environmental and health effects of the disposal, unsound recycling, or illegal exports of plastic waste fractions (Lincoln et al., 2007; Ogunseitan et al., 2009; Lovo and Rawlings, 2024). EEE is, thus, a critical sector to consider when increasing the circularity of plastics. While various circularity strategies, such as repair and circular design, are gaining prominence, recycling remains a crucial option with significant scope for future improvement (Future, 2024).

Recycling plastics used in EEE, however, presents several distinct challenges. Firstly, compared to other sectors, such as packaging, the EEE sector encompasses a wide variety of products, ranging from smartphones to refrigerators, which vary significantly in their material composition and function (Foelster et al., 2016; Babbitt et al., 2020). Consequently, the plastics used

⁴ Note, that the literature distinguishes between the notion of *consistency* and the related but broader concept of *coherence* (Herlin-Karnell and Konstadinides, 2013; De Baere, 2008; de Waal, 2021). As highlighted in de Waal (2021), consistency has been defined as a necessary but not sufficient condition of legal coherence. In this article, we focus on evaluating policy mix consistency without systematically analyzing additional criteria of policy mix coherence.

in EEE consist of a diverse mixture of (primarily engineering) polymers, including ABS, HIPS, and PC/ABS, often combined with various additives (Bill et al., 2019; Wagner et al., 2020). The diversity of plastics in EEE poses significant technical challenges in producing plastic recyclates from WEEE that meet certain quality & purity requirements (Ragaert et al., 2017; Cardamone et al., 2021). Secondly, plastics in EEE often contain various hazardous substances, such as brominated flame retardants, phthalates, and heavy metals (Wagner and Schlummer, 2020; Bill et al., 2022; Fjäder et al., 2022), which pose significant challenges to sorting and recycling processes. Recyclers must address health risks to workers and consumers of products containing recyclates and ensure that hazardous substances are managed in an environmentally sound manner (Bill et al., 2019; Cardamone et al., 2021; Fjäder et al., 2022). Thirdly, the EEE sector faces significant limitations in data availability regarding the quantity and composition of WEEE plastics (Cardamone et al., 2021; Babbitt et al., 2020). This lack of reliable data hinders operators' ability to timely adjust their processes in response to changes in the quality and quantity of e-plastics. These technical, safety, and data-related challenges help explain why currently only approximately 3% of plastics used in EEE originate from recycled material (Plastics Europe, 2022).

The EU has introduced a set of instruments to transition towards a circular plastic economy focusing on recycling. This policy mix aims to change the existing value chain structures and transform plastic product design, production, and use in different sectors, including EEE (European Commission, 2018a). Increasing plastics recycling in EEE will require both increases in the supply of recycled material (e.g., through the increased collection) as well as increased uptake of recycled materials in new EEE products (Klotz et al., 2022; Baldé et al., 2024).

Existing policy analyses have characterized the current policy landscape as complex, fragmented, and containing competing goals and visions (Domenech and Bahn-Walkowiak, 2019). Yet a systematic sectoral assessment of policy mixes for circularity is lacking: No comprehensive database gathers policies relevant to a circular plastics transition for different European sectors, such as EEE. Moreover, it remains unclear how various policies affect the distinct value chain steps and processes related to plastics recycling in EEE. This study aims to address this gap and provides an in-depth description of the policy mix for plastics recycling in the EEE sector. We build upon the literature analyzing the policy landscape for circularity and plastics (Milios, 2018; Wilts and O'Brien, 2019; Diana et al., 2022) but add a more systematic and sector-specific evaluation of how the current policy mix affects plastics recycling through the lens of three policy mix characteristics.

4. Methodology

4.1. Research design

Our assessment of the policy mix involves three analytical stages: first, we define and select the scope of the policy mix for the research case (*policy mix delineation*). Second, we identify and classify the instrument mix at the value chain level (*policy mix mapping*). Third, we qualitatively assess the characteristics of the policy mix (*policy mix evaluation*). This analytical approach combines deductive content analysis of legal documents with inductive case study research based on interviews and workshops with policymakers and different actors of the EEE value chain (Yin, 2008; Flick, 2023). This research design is deemed particularly suitable for evaluating policy mixes early in their implementation. The deductive content analysis yields an in-depth descriptive analysis of the current plastic policy mix in the EEE sector. Complementing these results with inductive case study research allows us to explore further the characteristics of the policy mix - a component of the policy mix literature that remains under-theorized (Eisenhardt and Graebner, 2007; Ossenbrink et al., 2019; Bach and Hansen, 2023). The corresponding data collection and analysis steps are highlighted in Fig. 2 and explained in the following section.

4.2. Data collection & analysis

As illustrated in Table 1, we collected data from legal documents (appendix, table B.1), stakeholder workshops, webinars (appendix, table B.2), public databases, and expert interviews (appendix, table B.3). The diverse data sources were analyzed and fed into our analysis at different stages.

In the first stage, we followed the recommendation in Ossenbrink et al. (2019) and delineated the policy mix for circularity at the EU level from both *top-down* and *bottom-up*. Hence, we first analyzed the key strategies at the EU level affecting circularity (European Commission, 2018a, 2020) and elicited the EU policies that are referenced in these documents. This initial list of policies was further complemented using desk research and public databases of policy instruments (OECD, 2023). The list of policies was triangulated using observational data from three webinars and one stakeholder workshop. The attended webinars were chosen as they focused explicitly on the regulatory landscape surrounding EEE recycling and gathered experts from different value chain steps. For the stakeholder workshop, we selected EEE recycling experts from different value chain positions as participants, including producer responsibility organisations (PROs), sorting and pretreatment facilities, plastic recyclers, EEE brand owners, and research institutes. The observational data from the webinars and the workshop was used to verify, complement, and narrow down our initial list of policies. This combination of bottom-up and top-down policy mix delineation left us with a set of ten EU policy and four strategy documents that are listed in appendix, table B.1.⁵

In the second stage of our analysis, we qualitatively coded the ten policy documents. We first developed a coding guideline that covers the main components of our analytical framework, including the policy strategies and instruments focusing on increasing

⁵ Note that a subset of workshop participants were pointing at the importance of food-contact and medical regulations. Since we focus on the entire electronic device sector, we decided to exclude these product-specific policies from our analysis.

Fig. 2. Research Design and data analysis.

Notes: This figure illustrates the research design applied in this study. The different steps of analysis are summarized in orange boxes. The data sources used at different steps are illustrated in gray boxes. Note that the 20 expert interviews were used to inform the mapping of the mix and its evaluation. The outcomes of each step are shown in the white ellipses.

Table 1
Overview of data sources.

Data source	Details	Full list
Interviews	20 semi-structured expert interviews	Table B.3
Legal documents	10 EU policy & 4 EU strategy documents	Table B.1
Workshops	1 stakeholder workshop with of various actors of the EEE value chain as well as researchers	Table B.2
Webinars & Conferences	3 online webinars & 1 stakeholder conference hosted by Circularity e.V.	Table B.2
Public databases	OECD Pine Database	

Notes: This table describes the main data sources used in the study. See referenced tables for more detailed information on each type of data source.

recycling or the uptake of recycled content.⁶ To consider the value chain level, we coded whenever an instrument was directly referencing a value chain actor — either as the obligor or obligee of the instrument. Three researchers then independently coded two sample texts to refine and operationalize the guideline. After finalizing the coding guideline (see table A.2 in the appendix), two researchers coded the remaining legal documents independently using the software Atlas.ti. The researchers compared and discussed the results of each coding block (2–3 legal texts) and refined the coding guideline where appropriate. The researchers then clustered the coded instruments and classified them along their type and purpose. Following Rogge and Reichardt (2016), we used the primary type and purposes in cases where instruments could not be clearly categorized into a single category.⁷ Referenced value chain actors were grouped into actor groups according to their value chain position — defined in this paper as plastics production, EEE product design and manufacturing, EEE product distribution and import, EEE product use and disposal, e-waste collection, e-waste treatment, disposal and shipment, and plastics recycling.⁸ The outcome of the instrument mapping is an inventory of 97 policy instruments and an overview of the key objectives and targets governing plastics recycling in the EEE sector in Europe. Tables 2 and 3 show an

⁶ In addition, we coded other influential variables such as the product and sector scope of each legislation and the legal definitions of target actors.

⁷ For example, extended producer responsibility *principles* are classified as sticks as they primarily make producers responsible for paying waste management practices. Modulated EPR fees, however, that would change according to the recyclability of a product, are classified as economic instruments as they aim to achieve behavior change (in product design) primarily through changes in prices (of waste management).

⁸ See Table C.5 in the appendix for the detailed actor grouping documentation. See, furthermore, figure 1 in the appendix for an illustration of the value chain steps.

Table 2
Example of instrument coding and classification output.

Variable	Example A	Example B
Legal text	<i>Member States shall ensure that producers or third parties acting on their behalf set up systems to provide for the recovery of WEEE using best available techniques. The systems may be set up by producers individually or collectively.</i>	<i>Member States shall make use of economic instruments and other measures to provide incentives for the application of the waste hierarchy, such as those indicated in Annex IVa or other appropriate instruments and measures.</i>
Instrument cluster	Requirements for the treatment and storage of separately collected WEEE	Economic incentives for applying the waste hierarchy
Instrument type	regulatory	economic
Instrument purpose	life-cycle safety & traceability	supply-push
Legislation	WEEE Directive	Waste Framework Directive
Year	2012	2018
Actor addressed	yes	no
Actor type	product producer/manufacturer	N/A

Notes: This table presents two examples of how instruments were coded and classified. Two researchers independently coded legislative texts for the presence of policy instruments and the actors they address. After comparing the coding results, the final list of coded elements was clustered by instrument topic. Instruments were then classified by type and purpose by the researchers.

Table 3
Example of strategy coding output.

Variable	Example A	Example B
Legal text	<i>EU chemicals policy and legislation, in particular REACH, encourage a shift to 'safe-by-design chemicals' through the progressive substitution of hazardous substances to better protect citizens and the environment. However, the safety of secondary raw materials can still be compromised, for instance, where banned substances persist in recycled feedstock.</i>	<i>Member states shall ensure that a minimum collection rate is achieved annually. From 2016, the minimum collection rate shall be 45% calculated on the basis of the total weight of WEEE collected in accordance with Articles 5 and 6 in a given year in the Member State concerned, expressed as a percentage of the average weight of EEE placed on the market in the three preceding years in that Member State. Member States shall ensure that the volume of WEEE collected evolves gradually during the period from 2016 to 2019 unless the collection rate laid down in the second subparagraph has already been achieved. From 2019, the minimum collection rate to be achieved annually shall be 65% of the average weight of EEE placed on the market in the three preceding years in the Member State concerned or alternatively, 85% of WEEE generated on the territory of that Member State.</i>
Objective cluster	Toxic free environment: address environmental and health concerns from chemicals	Increase circularity, reduce waste
Strategy type	Objective	Quantitative target
Legislative document	New Circular Economy Action Plan	WEEE Directive
Year	2020	2012

Notes: This table presents two examples of how policy strategies were coded and classified in this study. One researcher coded strategy documents for overarching objective and quantitative targets. The final list of coded elements was then clustered into three main objectives. Each coded text bit was further classified by its type (i.e., objective or quantitative target).

example of this inventory for the coded instruments and strategies, respectively. The full list of all coded and classified instruments can be found in table C.4 of the appendix. The policy inventory was used to provide a descriptive overview of the policy mix, e.g., through analyzing the number of instrument types, purposes, and referenced value chain actors.

In addition to the legal text analysis, we conducted 20 semi-structured interviews. Interviewees were selected using heterogeneity sampling to capture both shared patterns and diverse perspectives on the policy mix across different stakeholder groups (Patton, 2002; Suri, 2011). Our sample selection ensured representation from key stakeholders of the EU electronics sector and policymaking: government officials, academic researchers, NGO representatives, and industry actors from various steps of the electronics value chain. The interviews combined questions on the processes of plastics recycling or using recycled content, the legal requirements actors are facing, as well as questions on how different experts evaluate the current policy mix.⁹ The objective of the interviews was threefold: first, they serve as a further source of verification of our list of policies and strategies. Second, they complement the mapping of the instrument mix by providing details about how legal requirements affect actors in their day-to-day business. Third,

⁹ See table A.1 in the appendix for a more detailed description of the interview guideline.

Table 4
Operationalization of policy mix characteristics.

Characteristic	Definition	Coding criteria	Example
Consistency	Degree of alignment and compatibility of policy mix elements ^a	Existence of <i>contradictions or trade-offs (synergies and complementarities)</i> between different instruments, strategies, or between instruments and strategies	“The problem is that the chemical legislation is working against circularity [...] For example, the PFAS that is debated everywhere now that will be regulated: [...] I know that you have [...] these PFAS polymers everywhere. In each and every polyethylene film that you produce you have a tiny portion of fluoroelastomers as a process aid. Now, will nothing be circular then?”
Comprehensiveness	Degree to which all market-system-, and institutional failures, and other barriers are addressed by the mix ^a	<i>Lack</i> of instruments or strategies; <i>Gaps</i> in existing strategies and instruments w.r.t. addressing market, institutional, and system failures	“Another problem is end of waste. [...]. [A]lthough we are now talking about it at least, we have no [harmonized] European rules on end-of-waste for plastics, which means that if we have our end-of-waste status for our plastics in [EU production country], and we have a customer in [EU destination country] [...] then we have to ask [the] end of waste status in [EU destination country] and we have to ask end of waste status in [EU transit countries] because the material drives through those countries. [...] And if one of them blocks, the whole matter blocks [...].”
Coordination	Degree of alignment of instruments between different actors of the value chain	Missing (Existing) <i>information interfaces</i> between different value chain actors; <i>Misalignment (Alignment)</i> of existing interfaces between actors	“[...] I think because it is on such a detailed level, that it does not reflect what is happening in our recycling process because our input is a diversity of materials. So having all the specific data, let us say, a calculator on component level, the amount of materials that it uses. It is basically useless. We cannot use it in this way [...].”

^a Definitions are based on De Baere (2008), Herlin-Karnell and Konstadinides (2013), Del Río (2014), Rogge and Reichardt (2016), Bach and Hansen (2023).
Notes: This table illustrates how the three policy mix characteristics, consistency, comprehensiveness, and coordination, were operationalized in this study. For each characteristic, coding criteria were laid out based on the definitions given in the literature. The researchers coded the interview data for text passages matching the criteria and further classified the coded text. The classification was based on whether the quote hinted at a specific characteristic's presence or absence (e.g., consistency between instruments or inconsistency between instruments) and at the policy element (strategy or instrument) it occurs.

and very decisively, insights from the interviews allowed us to evaluate the characteristics of the current policy mix — which cannot be inferred from the analysis of the legal text only.

In the last stage of our analysis, we use the legal instrument inventory and interview results to assess how the policy mix affects plastics recycling and the use of recyclates in the EEE sector. This evaluation uses the above-defined policy mix characteristics, consistency, comprehensiveness, and coordination as structuring elements. Given that policy mixes for plastics circularity have gained little attention in the literature, and no benchmark exists for how such mixes *should* be designed, we rely on literature from other sustainability contexts when operationalizing the policy mix characteristics. We elicit specific criteria derived from the definition of each characteristic and their operationalization in the context of renewable energy (see, e.g. Reichardt and Rogge, 2016; Rogge and Reichardt, 2016) and complement these criteria inductively with how actors perceived them in the interviews. Table 4 gives an overview of the operationalization. We then coded each interview based on the occurrence of the coding criteria for policy mix characteristics (as outlined in Table 4). Finally, coded segments for different policy mix characteristics were clustered by the policy instrument or strategy they referred to and cross-checked using the legal inventory.

Our methodological approach does not give a systematic assessment of the *degree* of fulfillment of characteristics.¹⁰ We, however, argue that our exploratory approach for analyzing the policy landscape through the lens of policy mix characteristics provides a valuable lens to detect the current policy barriers and drivers for increasing circularity.

5. Results

This section presents the results of the analysis of the policy mix governing plastics recycling in EEE. We first provide a descriptive overview and interpretation of the policy mix strategy. We then present the main findings of the policy mix evaluation along the three policy mix characteristics in focus, (1) consistency, (2) comprehensiveness, and (3) coordination. We finally summarize and

¹⁰ See, e.g., Bach and Hansen (2023) who determine whether policy mixes are weakly or strongly consistent and comprehensive.

interpret the results and explain in more depth whether the current policy mix is conducive to increasing recycled content along the EEE value chain.

5.1. Policy mix strategy

The EU strategy documents to support the transition to a circular plastics economy are focused on three key objectives: Environmental and human health risks from chemicals shall be reduced, circularity increased, and a resilient internal market shall be maintained (see Fig. 3). More concrete and sector-specific targets further substantiate these generic cross-sector objectives. For EEE, targets specifically concern the supply of recycled content, but they merely address waste collection and aim at the end-of-life stage rather than EEE design or production. Member states (MS) and state organs (e.g., municipalities) are accountable for fulfilling and reporting these collection and recovery targets. Yet, through the existing EPR scheme,¹¹ this is in part channeled to OEMs and distributors. Thus far, no quantitative targets exist in support of the social long-term objectives of a circular plastics economy (e.g., related to chemical safety and consumers) or to enhance the resilience of the EU single market. Rather than quantitative EEE targets, qualitative cross-sector targets prevail in the strategy. These include critical revisions of legislation that address all three main strategic objectives (see Fig. 3).

Overall, the EU policy mix strategy is tailored towards the specificities of the circular plastics economy in EEE but also exposes its complexities. The legal revisions intend to foster and balance all three key objectives shown in Fig. 3, but long-term guidance on their integration is absent. This is similar for the legal domains: legislative provisions relevant to the target of recycled content exist in all three domains, yet ensuring the interconnectedness is mostly part of single policy processes and not supported by an overarching strategy or policy. The EU has recognized this as a pivotal issue for the transition. Still, a resolution from 2018 on this issue focused only on a handful of critical themes, of which some remain unaddressed to date (European Commission, 2018b). Finally, quantitative targets mainly raise ambitions for long-existing supply-side targets for collection and waste recovery and command no radical shift.

5.2. Consistency: Conflicts between substance restrictions and increasing recycled content

A policy mix can be deemed consistent if different strategies and instruments do not contradict. Within the EU policy mix for plastics recycling in EEE, tensions arise between promoting circularity and ensuring chemical safety. At the strategy level, this tension is not evident: circularity goals target increased recovery of WEEE, while chemical safety objectives require that the various hazardous additives contained in WEEE plastics are removed before entering recycling channels. Looking in more depth at the implementation of these strategies at the policy instrument level, however, reveals a trade-off between chemical safety and increasing circularity. The policy mix for circular plastics includes various instruments to restrict or ban hazardous chemicals.¹² Value chain actors affected by such measures are producers of new substances, manufacturers of electronic devices, and plastic recyclers. In practice, two key developments conflict to increase recycling and recycled content (Interview 2, Interview 5). Firstly, threshold values for hazardous substances in products, for instance, PBDEs in the POP regulation, are being reduced (European Parliament and the Council, 2019; Council of the European Union, 2022). Certainly, reducing limit values for hazardous substances creates benefits to human health and the environment (Interview 4, Interview 19).¹³ However, a sudden reduction of thresholds can create significant compliance difficulties and added costs for recyclers (Interview 14, Interview 15, Interview 16). For example, larger samples are needed to detect lower substance limit values for recyclers when testing their output for the presence of hazardous substances (Interview 11, Interview 14), which is impracticable on a daily basis (Interview 15).¹⁴ Moreover, recyclers often cannot test for low-limit values themselves but must involve external laboratories, creating additional costs and practicability issues (Interview 15, Interview 16). In the short to medium run, these developments can mean that plastics in WEEE fractions subject to substance restrictions cannot be separated in an economically viable way. Recyclers may rather send all e-plastics to incineration or other channels instead of putting in the effort to sort out hazardous fractions and recycle the rest (Interview 5, Interview 14, Interview 16). As argued by a former manager of a plastics recycling company, threshold levels that are being discussed for some POP substances effectively mean that “[...] the European Union would say ‘stop recycling’ [of e-plastics]”. (Interview 16:53). Secondly, chemical regulation in the EU appears to be moving from restricting single substances towards regulating groups or families of substances that share similar properties.¹⁵ Such family or property-based regulation offers various advantages (see, e.g. Muellers et al., 2023), but in the short-run, they pose similar financial and compliance barriers to recyclers and other waste management operators.¹⁶ Moreover, a conflict emerges between the policy mix strategy objective to innovate for increasing recycled content (and hence ensure the competitiveness of the internal market) and the property-based bans. Legacy chemicals are expected to remain circulating for decades

¹¹ Extended producer responsibility schemes make product producers responsible for waste management of their products. They are a means to shift waste management costs from municipalities and taxpayers to product producers (Laubinger et al., 2021).

¹² For example, some long-used additives, such as phthalate plasticizers, are meanwhile characterized as substances of very high concern (SVHC) and subject to REACH regulation (Bakhiyi et al., 2018; Wagner and Schlummer, 2020; Bill et al., 2022).

¹³ See, e.g., Wemken et al. (2020), van der Schyff et al. (2023), Ma et al. (2024) for the case of flame retardant restrictions and its impacts on human health.

¹⁴ Threshold levels are met in the first instance by plastic producers and EEE manufacturers. However, they merely offer an indication to recyclers on the expected composition of the recycled content, as contamination in the use phase and cross-contamination from disposal and collection are frequent.

¹⁵ See in particular the current proposal to restrict the manufacturing, placing on the market, and use of PFAS (European Chemicals Agency, 2023, 2024).

¹⁶ EU chemical legislation generally considers these short-term challenges by including transition periods, giving the relevant stakeholders time to adapt to the new requirements. Such transition periods alone, however, may not be enough to spur investment into new sorting and recycling technologies needed to ensure compliance.

Fig. 3. Policy strategy of the mix governing circular plastics.
Notes: This figure gives an overview of the strategies linked to enabling a circular plastics economy in EEE. Blue boxes denote objectives and targets elicited from strategy documents, while gray boxes refer to objectives and targets formulated in the policy documents. The upper part summarizes the three main and associated sector-specific (EEE) objectives. The bottom half highlights the quantitative policy targets formulated for each objective. NA stands for the absence of quantitative targets.

in products with longer lifetimes, and a restriction for all value chain actors simultaneously hinders recyclers’ development of new separation techniques unless legal provisions are to create exceptions to experimentation for the treatment of banned chemicals. According to a former manager of a recycling plant, “[i]t’s impossible to [innovate] and be at the lowest possible threshold from day one. You have to learn to work with these new separation techniques”. (Interview 16:46)

5.3. Comprehensiveness: Gaps in end-of-waste definitions and methods for calculating recycled content

Policy mixes are characterized as comprehensive if they contain no gaps and address all relevant market, system, and institutional failures. Our analysis of policy instrument types and purposes reveals that the policy mix for plastics recycling contains gaps in economic and demand-pull instruments. Fig. 4 shows that there is a clear prevalence of regulatory instrument types (sticks) with only a small number of economic instruments (carrots), which are found dominantly in waste-related policies. While this low number of

Fig. 4. Distribution of policy instruments by type (left) and purpose (right) over time.

Notes: This figure shows the distribution of policy instrument types and purposes over time. The height of the bars represents the number of policy instruments introduced in a given year, while the color indicates its type (left side graph) and purpose (right side graph). The category *Other* was used where an instrument could not be clearly classified into the three purpose categories.

EU-wide economic instruments does not reflect the various economic instruments that member states have implemented for waste management at the national level,¹⁷ our findings reveal that concerted EU measures are lacking, e.g., to internalize the cost of pollution from waste through green taxation schemes or to incentivize the uptake of recycled content (Mottershead et al., 2021). *Instrument purposes* relate dominantly to life-cycle safety & traceability across all three policy domains (see Fig. 4 and table C.4 in appendix). Several instruments for stimulating the supply of recycled content were introduced in the waste domain between 1999 and 2020 as part of the WFD and the WEEE Directives. Remarkably, instruments aimed at stimulating demand for recycled content were absent until 2024. This strongly affects EEE device manufacturers' choice of virgin materials over recycled content and ultimately hinders supply by recyclers and investment into new recycling technologies (Vogt et al., 2021; Aristi Capetillo et al., 2023; Brown and Börkey, 2024). In addition to these findings, we identified two essential gaps in the comprehensiveness of the EU policy mix that, if addressed, could stimulate market-based demand without creating direct demand instruments: A mandatory calculation and verification method of recycled plastic content along the value chain and harmonized end-of-waste criteria (Interview 2, Interview 7, Brown and Börkey, 2024).

International certification schemes and standards for calculating recycled content exist, including harmonized standards at the EU level (Shamsuyeva and Endres, 2021). However, the lack of compulsory legal provisions enables false recycled content claims to go unnoticed. Existing voluntary certification schemes differ in several key aspects, particularly regarding the inclusion of pre-consumer waste in recycled content definitions (Interview 19, Brown and Börkey, 2024). They also vary in the chain of custody methods used to ensure the life-cycle safety & traceability of recycled plastic materials throughout the supply chain (Interview 2, Brown and Börkey, 2024). The lack of mandatory certification schemes creates an uneven playing field for producers and users of recycled content (Interview 2, Interview 7, Interview 14), undermining buyers' trust in recycled plastic materials. As a policy expert representing European producers of electric appliances pointed out, "[t]here's a possibility for unscrupulous players [...] placing the product on the market [...], [without] the right information going to the consumer at the end of the day [...]" (Interview 7:27).

The lack of harmonized end-of-waste criteria is a second gap in the current policy mix (Interview 5, Interview 9, Interview 14). End-of-waste criteria define when waste ceases to be waste and receives product status after recycling or other recovery processes. A product status typically increases the scope of outlets for the recovered materials (Johansson and Forsgren, 2020).¹⁸ There are ongoing efforts to establish EU-wide end-of-waste criteria for plastics (European Commission et al., 2024b), but varying definitions have been adopted at the member-state level (European Commission, 2022a), leading to additional export and import restrictions set by national rather than EU laws. This impacts the competitiveness of recycled content and acts as a barrier to increasing both the supply of and demand for recycled content. OEMs, recyclers, and other actors in the value chain can face increased administrative and financial burdens when shipping material across different EU member states as the legal status of recovered material will vary (Interview 1, Interview 14).

5.4. Coordination: Deficits of information interfaces between recyclers and producers

Policy mixes are considered coordinated when instruments effectively engage all relevant actors and are well-aligned throughout the value chain. In the context of the circular economy (CE), a crucial aspect of coordination is establishing interfaces that facilitate

¹⁷ See, e.g., European Environmental Agency (2023) for an overview of these instruments and their applications.

¹⁸ Note, however, that the harmonization of end-of-waste criteria will typically not change outlets for fractions containing hazardous substances, as these are subject to chemical legislation.

Fig. 5. Overview of policy instruments along the value chain.

Notes: This figure shows which value chain actors are affected by the different policy instruments. Part (a) depicts which of the instruments in the mix directly reference any value chain actor. The sum of the vertical bars represents the total number of instruments included in the mix (97 instruments). Part (b) illustrates which value chain actors are referenced in the instruments that specified actors. The sum of vertical bars represents the total amount of actor references across all instruments that reference actors (66 instruments). Instruments that explicitly target product users are highlighted in yellow. Part (c) depicts which life-cycle safety & traceability instruments address the actors of the EEE value chain. The sum of vertical bars represents the total number of actor references in all life-cycle safety & traceability instruments (53 instruments).

information flow across the value chain. Our evaluation of the policy mix for plastics recycling in EEE highlights two main coordination issues at different steps of the life-cycle of plastics.

First, product users remain underaddressed by the current policy mix. As highlighted in Fig. 5 part b, only a few measures explicitly address product users¹⁹. Whereas several regulatory instruments have been introduced to ensure knowledge regarding hazardous substances, product safety, and product sustainability²⁰ is shared along the value chain, the flow of information often breaks down once a product enters its use phase. Specifically, the EU policy mix lacks adequate information and economic instruments to engage product users in the collection and sorting of e-waste, e.g., by disposing of their old electrical and EEE separately. Consequently, large amounts of WEEE are either hoarded or discarded in municipal solid waste (MSW) and never reach appropriate recycling channels (Interview 7, Interview 14, Interview 18, Baldé et al., 2022). For the collection of WEEE, this means that there is a lack of coordination “[...] between what the consumer does with his end-of-life product and the responsibility that the producer has to collect and properly treat it [...]” (Interview 14:39).

A second coordination issue arises at the intersection between product producers and waste treatment and recycling operators. Our analysis of policy instruments in Fig. 5 part c and table C.2 in the appendix shows that the EU has introduced a variety of life-cycle safety & traceability instruments that collectively address the multiple actors of the value chain. Among these are several instruments aimed at reducing information asymmetries between actors involved in upstream production and downstream waste recovery (Interview 4, Nicolli et al., 2012). Looking at these instruments in more detail, however, reveals several misalignments. A recent information instrument aimed to connect substance and product producers with recyclers is the SCIP database on hazardous substances in products (Friege et al., 2021; PWC, 2022).²¹ The platform was intended to assist waste management operators in detecting hazardous substances but has substantial shortcomings from the perspective of plastic recyclers. To access the product-specific information, recyclers would need to read out product IDs, which are typically not visible anymore after use, collection, and shredding of WEEE (Interview 5, Interview 8, Friege et al., 2021; PWC, 2022). Moreover, since no enforcement mechanism exists for producers to provide the relevant information, the database remains patchy (PWC, 2022). Another newly developed

¹⁹ Note that only about two-thirds of instruments in the mix directly reference the value chain actor they target. In some cases, this is because the instruments will be further specified at the member state or municipal levels (particularly in the case of EU directives). Other instruments apply to the entire value chain or are vaguely designed without explicitly identifying the target actor.

²⁰ The information provisions regarding product sustainability are part of the *Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation*. The exact requirements are defined in delegated acts that have not yet entered into force.

²¹ This instrument requires the suppliers of products to report information on SVHCs contained in their products to ECHA. It has been amended to the Waste Framework Directive in 2018 (European Parliament and the Council, 2018).

information instrument, the digital product passport (DPP), may still not be adequately tailored to meet the information needs for waste treatment and recycling. The DPP – introduced in the *Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation* – is designed to store sustainability-related information about products, their components, and materials throughout the entire value chain (European Parliament and the Council, 2024). While the exact design of the DPP is yet to be determined, recyclers expressed concern that they cannot process the information stored on the DPP, if it is accessible only through barcodes on final products (Interview 4, Interview 5). Furthermore, the burden placed on various value chain actors to provide detailed information about product materials and components is disproportionate to the benefits for recyclers who still need to test material composition on-site to ensure safety and proper recycling treatment (Interview 7, Interview 14). In the context of EEE recycling, the existing proposal poses the risk of gathering extensive information that “[...] doesn’t reflect what’s happening in [the] recycling process [...]” (Interview 15:57). A DPP can be most valuable in the initial recycling stages, if it provides information on how different materials are combined and how final products can be dismantled for further treatment. This crucial information is currently not included in the planned design of the DPP (Interview 15), even though the DPP can only be fully evaluated after its implementation. Despite its current limitations, policy experts and PROs view the DPP’s approach to coordinating value chain information exchange as a positive development (Interview 4, Interview 5). The DPP can reduce information gaps between production, consumption, and recovery stages of the product life-cycle (Interview 4, Interview 5, Chaudhuri et al., 2024) and has the potential to enable new sorting processes and technologies (Plociennik et al., 2024).

5.5. Summary & interpretation of results

Our analysis of the policy mix in EEE has revealed a list of issues for increasing plastics recycling and the use of recycled plastics content in EEE. As summarized in Fig. 6, these issues can be categorized based on three key policy mix characteristics (consistency, comprehensiveness, and coordination) and the seven value chain steps where they predominantly arise. First, we find that chemical substance restrictions create conflicts at the plastics recycling stage, potentially impeding innovation in new sorting technologies and reducing e-plastic recycling in the short term. Second, our results indicate significant gaps in the policy mix across various steps of the value chain. For plastic production and EEE manufacturers, there are insufficient economic and demand-pull instruments to level the playing field between virgin and recycled plastics. Moreover, the absence of mandatory rules for calculating recycled content hinders efforts to prevent greenwashing and build trust in recycled materials. For recyclers, the lack of harmonized end-of-waste criteria within the EU imposes an administrative burden when shipping waste and recovered materials across member states. Third, our analysis highlights coordination issues within the current policy mix. There are not enough policy measures to address product users, creating difficulties in increasing the separate collection of WEEE. Additionally, information gaps between producers and recyclers complicate the recycling process. The recently introduced information instruments are not yet sufficiently tailored to close these gaps and to significantly facilitate plastics recycling in EEE.

6. Discussion

The transition to a circular plastics economy, as advocated by the EU, is a complex challenge. It requires a policy mix that fosters the technical, economic, and societal innovations necessary to shift from the current fossil-fuel-based linear plastics economy to one that minimizes the use of non-renewable and virgin materials. In this study, we focused on the transition following one circular economy strategy, recycling, which the EU had defined as one of several critical areas that need policy intervention. We examined the current policy mix by focusing on the actors involved in reconfiguring plastic life-cycle management over the value chain. In combining three policy mix characteristics (consistency, comprehensiveness, coordination) with this value chain perspective, we found that the current policy mix exhibits several critical barriers, i.e., it entails policy conflicts, gaps, and misalignments of actors and processes. Although the circular economy and recycling objectives are integrated into the EEE policy mix, our case study suggests that it is not conducive to substantially directing and accelerating the transition toward a circular plastics economy in the short- and medium-term.

A contributing factor is that many of the policies in the mix were not initially designed to facilitate a circular economy transition and predate the EU’s first circular economy strategy (European Commission, 2015). The current policy mix has been modified multiple times to include CE objectives. Nevertheless, its policies are still insufficiently designed to (1) balance the different objectives of the circular economy plastics transition, (2) integrate the different legislative domains of product, waste, and chemical legislation, and (3) facilitate and moderate the circular value chain reconfiguration.²² An evolutionary view on circular economy transitions offers a theoretical explanation for such “unsynchronized policies” (Chizaryfard et al., 2021). According to this view, established technologies, industries, and governing institutions create structural lock-ins through their complex interactions. Breaking these structural lock-ins demands co-evolution of all three elements (Aminoff and Sundqvist-Andberg, 2021; Chizaryfard et al., 2021). “Unsynchronized policies” are thus reflective of unharmonious changes in these elements, creating temporary misalignments and tensions.

²² In addition, EU policy mixes are only a part of the larger landscape of policy mixes that EEE value chain actors are subject to. For example, national economic and innovation policies can be equally decisive in guiding their activities.

Fig. 6. Overview of policy mix framework and analysis results.

Notes: This figure summarizes the results of the qualitative evaluation of the EU policy mix for plastics recycling in EEE. Our findings are structured along three characteristics (y-axis) and the seven life-cycle steps of plastics in EEE products (x-axis).

6.1. Integrating waste, chemical, and product legislation

We identified key tensions by focusing on the salient issues of chemical safety. The revision of waste policies (e.g. the Waste Framework or WEEE Directive) expanded instruments for material recovery. However, ensuring the safety of these recovered materials for human health and the environment demands greater alignment between previously separate legislative domains (Alaranta and Turunen, 2021) involving the adaptation of technologies, institutions, and industrial practices. Although there may be less tension between these objectives and other CE strategies like *reduce*, our results indicate that significant conflicts arise for recycling. Strict criteria for quality and purity of materials, as established by chemical and product legislation, in practice, result in specific fractions of waste being discarded for recycling. This conflict is amplified by emerging safety challenges specific to CE and recycling, which are not adequately addressed in current chemical legislation. Recyclers and other recovery operators face distinct challenges in ensuring the safety of recovered materials compared to primary substance producers. Yet, both actor groups are governed under the same regulation with minimal adjustments to promote a circular economy. This does not imply that the safety of secondary materials should be jeopardized for increasing circularity (Johansson and Krook, 2021; Alaranta and Turunen, 2021). Instead, there is a need for policy action to better integrate the distinct policy domains of waste, product, and chemical legislation (European Commission, 2018b). To strengthen the interface and accelerate the circular economy plastics transition, it is crucial to improve the traceability of substances along the value chain.²³ This could, for instance, involve enhancing existing instruments like the SCIP database or the DPP by requiring substance and product producers to share information on hazardous substances in their products. As other research suggests (see, e.g. Alaranta and Turunen, 2021), these instruments should be expanded to include strict enforcement mechanisms for reporting, and their scope should cover not only hazardous substances but also those that impede recyclability. Another way to better integrate the domains of waste, product, and chemical policy is through introducing ecodesign guidelines emphasizing recyclability and (hazardous) waste generation requirements as a critical aspect of sustainability. As highlighted in European Commission et al. (2024a), such ecodesign rules can be designed for specific products and sectors but

²³ Traceability of substances has, for example, been discussed intensively during the INC process leading towards a plastics treaty.

should also be considered to cover plastics and polymer production entirely. Additionally, adjusted extended producer responsibility (EPR) fees based on a product's recyclability (Mayers et al., 2013; Dubois and Peters, 2016; Micheaux and Aggeri, 2021) could serve as a strong incentive. As WEEE differs in many dimensions from other sectors, such as packaging where EPR schemes are already established²⁴, the fee design and especially its modulations should account for that. For example, as product lifetime is comparably high, the fee should not only finance the recycling infrastructure but could instead focus on financing repair and refurbishment facilities.

6.2. Filling instrument gaps at the demand-side

To effectively address the environmental externalities of the linear plastics economy and make recycled plastics cost-competitive with virgin materials, additional instruments are needed to either stimulate demand for recycled content or discourage the use of virgin alternatives (Nicolli et al., 2012; OECD, 2018; Aristi Capetillo et al., 2023). However, such measures are not sufficiently incorporated into the EU policy mix. Most instruments ensure that products and waste management processes avoid harm to human health and the environment. Only a few stimulate the supply of recycled materials, e.g., by increasing waste collection. The critical question of how recovered waste is reintegrated into upstream production – a vital aspect of the circular economy transition – has been largely neglected (Ghisellini and Ulgiati, 2020). Nevertheless, recent policymaking is undergoing a shift in focus: Policies like the *Ecodesign for Sustainability Regulation* and the proposed *Directive on Green Claims* (European Parliament and the Council, 2023a) are beginning to emphasize the demand side for recovered materials. Such demand-side instruments can take various forms, including transparency rules on environmental claims, recycled content quotas, and green public procurement guidelines (Interview 7, The World Bank, 2022). Still, timing is crucial when introducing measures to stimulate demand for recycled materials. EU policymakers should prioritize establishing a mandatory calculation method for recycled content to provide a level playing field for buyers and suppliers of recycled plastics. Additionally, when setting recycled content targets, care must be taken to avoid targets that push demand beyond the supply of high-quality recyclates, as this could inflate prices and result in high premiums for consumers (Brown and Börkey, 2024).

6.3. Moving from sectoral to value-chain legislation

Finally, a significant issue in the EEE policy mix that relates specifically to the requirements underlying a circular economy transition is the challenge to attain better interlinkages among policy domains and value chain actors and their processes. Recent legislation on batteries and end-of-life vehicles is shifting away from the traditional separation of waste and product legislation towards a “[...] value chain approach [...]” (Interview 4:39). These policies integrate provisions across the entire product life-cycle, including rules on financing end-of-life vehicle management and mandatory quotas for recycled plastics content in new products (European Parliament and the Council, 2023b). In the EEE sector, the legacy of established policies and institutions, such as those related to chemical safety, seems to hinder the adoption of this more integrated approach, but more attention to connecting policy domains and value chain actors holds significant potential to advance the circular economy transition. Accordingly, the EU has introduced funding mechanisms for circular economy projects encouraging collaboration between different actor groups (see, e.g. European Commission, 2024). Upcoming strategies should build on these schemes and more explicitly focus on critical materials, components, and products within the EU rather than being limited to specific sectors or technologies. For materials, such as plastics, ‘closing the loop’ through CE strategies is a cross-sectoral endeavor. For example, more cross-sectoral policy designs that engage consumers in the circular economy transition are necessary. Additionally, the EU increasingly relies on private actors’ self-organization capabilities within value chains, particularly as policy frameworks combine public policies with both public and private standards. To manage this complexity, existing national orchestrating organizations – such as national research councils²⁵ – could be given explicit EU-level mandates. These organizations, which already serve as independent agencies integrating stakeholder views and implementing policy instruments at the national level, could, for example, help oversee all value chain positions are included in relevant consultation and standardization processes.

7. Conclusions

This study analyzed how the current EU policy mix contributes to plastics recycling and the use of recycled plastics in the EEE sector. We argued that the EU policy mix, in its current form, is not substantially driving the transition toward a circular plastics economy and discussed potential solutions. EU policymakers could address three key areas towards a more consistent, comprehensive, and coordinated policy mix: First, improving the interface between chemical, waste, and product legislation to resolve tensions between increasing recyclate uptake and phasing out hazardous substances in EEE. Second, introducing mandatory rules for calculating recycled content while implementing economic incentives for recyclate use. Third, the policy mix should engage all value chain actors, including product users, and ensure that information instruments are designed to fit the requirements of relevant actors, including waste management operators.

Our analysis adds to the most recent empirical literature that systematically applies the policy mix framework introduced by Rogge and Reichardt (2016) to the circular economy transition (see, e.g. Ladu et al., 2020; Entsaló et al., 2023). A significant

²⁴ See, e.g. Joltreau (2022) for a recent evaluation of EPR packaging schemes in the EU.

²⁵ See, for example, the Research Councils of Norway, France, or Belgium and specialized national innovation funds such as Sitra in Finland.

difference to the energy transition, where the framework has been most often applied (see, e.g. Peters et al., 2012; Nunez-Jimenez et al., 2022), is that the policy landscape for a circular economy is less mature, containing fewer stringent instruments and only a few quantitative targets. We argue that our adjusted framework provides a vital extension that allows studying and evaluating policy mixes early in their implementation. We also confirmed that the characteristics of the policy mix, consistency, comprehensiveness, and coordination, are valuable for analyzing the CE transition policy mix. Additionally, we demonstrated that our proposed characteristic, coordination, offers further insight into policy mix design issues that the established categories do not address. This characteristic is specified at the value chain level and can capture how well instruments are aligned between different players in the supply chain.

By analyzing the policy mix as it exists today, our study has focused on the outcome of policy design rather than the process that led to the policy formulation (May, 2003; Howlett and Rayner, 2013). While this approach reveals critical design issues from the value chain actors' perspective, future research should complement our findings and examine the mechanisms and processes underlying circular economy policy mix design.²⁶ Such research could, for instance, highlight the complex challenges EU policymakers encounter in establishing harmonized definitions for end-of-waste status and recycled content, thereby informing more nuanced policy recommendations that address context-specific implementation barriers.

Combining manual coding of legal documents with semi-structured interviews allowed for an in-depth assessment of the EU policy mix for plastics recycling. Our method can serve as a blueprint for assessing other CE strategies, such as reuse, repair, and reduce, where policies are currently limited.²⁷ The detailed legal analysis involved certain trade-offs. Conceptually, this paper represents a technoscientific analysis at the practice stage (Korhonen et al., 2018) focusing on the assessment of concrete instruments rather than normative discussions about paradigm and vision changes in policy-making. We acknowledge that the transition to a circular plastics economy is not merely a technical question of 'getting the right policies' or 'getting policies right'. Still, the article highlights the role of policy mixes as one structural factor for establishing the required institutional capacities and framework conditions for the transition (Chizaryfard et al., 2021).

Methodologically, the selection of key EU policies governing plastics recycling in EEE followed established procedures, including iterative refinement and triangulation across multiple data sources (Ossenbrink et al., 2019). However, given the resource-intensive nature of manual coding of legal texts, we focused our analysis on 14 core EU policies while acknowledging that other relevant policies fell outside this article's scope.²⁸ Moreover, while notable differences exist in national implementation of EU directives and member state-specific legislation,²⁹ this analysis focuses solely on EU-wide policies, excluding both national variations and the broader alignment of EU policy with global efforts toward a circular plastics economy.³⁰

Future policy mix analyses could benefit from text-as-data methods to systematically extract policy elements and strategies from legal texts (Sewerin et al., 2023).³¹ Such computational approaches would allow researchers to examine CE policy mixes at scale, spanning multiple CE strategies, materials, and national & international legislation. However, the application of these methods is still emerging, and comprehensive EU-level CE policy databases are not yet available. The theoretical framework and coding guideline we applied for analyzing the plastics recycling mix could, therefore, provide guidance for advancing text-as-data methods in CE policy research (Sewerin et al., 2023).

CRedit authorship contribution statement

David Pfeffer: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Denise Reike:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Catharina R. Bening:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary material related to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eist.2025.100982>.

²⁶ As Capano and Lippi (2017) and Howlett and Rayner (2013) note, policymakers must balance multiple theoretical and practical principles when designing policy mixes, making it challenging to achieve full consistency, coordination, and comprehensiveness in practice.

²⁷ These CE strategies are arguably even more vital for transitioning to a circular plastics economy that respects planetary boundaries, lowers overall plastic production, and induces more profound behavioral and socio-cultural changes.

²⁸ Most prominent policies and instruments that have not been included in our analysis are economic or financial RDI instruments, included in EU's *Framework for State Aid for Research and Development and Innovation* (European Commission, 2022b) or other financial policies such as the Public Procurement Directive (European Parliament and the Council, 2014) and the EU Taxonomy Regulation (European Parliament and the Council, 2020).

²⁹ These variations include different approaches to plastics taxation (WTS Global, 2024) and EPR schemes (Favot et al., 2022).

³⁰ See, for instance, the current negotiations for a Global Plastics Treaty (UNEP, 2022).

³¹ Recent applications of text-as-data methods in policy research include Capano et al. (2020), Ash et al. (2021), Firebanks-Quevedo et al. (2022).

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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